

Gran Telescopio Canarias

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GRANTECAN

The organization

- **GTC** telescope is an initiative of the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC)
- Funded by Spain (90%), México (5%), and the University of Florida (2.5-5%). China in the process of becoming a new member
- Belongs to the set of Spanish *Unique Scientific & Technical Infrastructures (ICTS)*
- Construction started in 2000, first light in 2007, operations started in 2009
- **GRANTECAN** is the company that built, operates, maintains and upgrades GTC

The telescope

10.4 m alt-az , Ritchey-Chrétien configuration: collecting area 73 m², focal length 169.9 m (plate scale 1.21 arcsec mm⁻¹)

M1: 36 hexagonal aluminium-coated Zerodur segments. Active-optics is provided by 108 positioners, 216 moment actuators, and 168 position sensors → 324 degrees of freedom

M2: aluminium-coated beryllium. 5 active degrees of freedom → alignment, chopping, tip-tilt corrections

Telescope:

- ~500 electromagnetic axes
- Moving mass 400 tons with 1 nm precision

Dome:

- Ø35m - 13m opening size
- 450 tons

GTC science instruments (2009- 2027)

GTC science instruments (2027)

GTC operational mode

- **>95% in service-queue mode**, which allows to:
 - adapt to environmental conditions and technical constraints maximising data quality
 - allow easy ingestion of targets of opportunity and projects with strict time constraints
 - reduce carbon footprint of travels
- **Visitor mode** also allowed
- **Remote visitor mode** under implementation

Next generation GTC instrumentation

1. **Extend AO development:** AO single conjugated → GLAO (ground-layer) → **MCAO** (dual conjugated), with FRIDA f.o.v. upgrade.

2. Develop a **multi-band (UV, VIS and NIR) imager and spectrograph**. Preliminary Market Consultation started.

Tender calls expected before the end of 2024.

Science highlights (Deep)

$>31 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$ (r' , 8.1 h)

Trujillo & Liri 2016, ApJ, 823, 123

SHARDS (240h OSIRIS) *P. Pérez González*

Science highlights (fast and accurate)

545 1-min spectra in two weeks

Muñoz-Darias et al. 2016, Nature, 534, 75

$P_{\text{orb}} = 2.15 \text{ h}$, $g = 19.6 \text{ mag}$

Sampling 5 sec (15s in u)

Rebassa-Mansergas et al. ,2019, Nature Astr.